

Synthesis and Studies on Heterocyclic Nitrogen Compounds

M. A. EL-MAGHRABY*, A. K. KHALAFALLA, M. E. HASSAN and H. A. SOLEIMAN

Chemistry Department, Aswan-Faculty of Science, Aswan, Egypt

Manuscript received 17 December 1985, accepted 3 August 1986

Condensation of 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazoline-5-one with 4-aminoacetophenone gave a quantitative yield of 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolidene-*p*-acetylaniline (1). Condensation of 1 with aromatic aldehydes yielded the corresponding pyrazolideneazomethine-chalcones (2a-f). Interaction of 2 with hydrazines, hydroxylamine, urea, and thiourea afforded a new pyrazolidene azomethine pyrazolines, isooxazoles, pyrimidine and pyrimidine thione derivatives, respectively.

PYRIMIDINE, isooxazoles, pyrimidine thione derivatives play a vital role in many biological processes¹⁻⁵ and as synthetic drugs. The chemistry of these heterocyclic compounds have been receiving much attention in the recent years. This is principally due to the unique physical and chemical properties of such compounds, which had gained their wide applications as plant growth regulators⁶, dyes⁷ and corrosion inhibitors⁸.

Results and Discussion

1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazoline-5-one condensed easily with *p*-aminoacetophenone in absolute ethanol and piperidine giving a quantitative yield of 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolidene-*p*-acetylaniline (1)

Condensation of 1 with aromatic aldehydes proceeded smoothly in dry alcohol in presence of piperidine as a catalyst to yield the corresponding 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-chalcones (2a-f).

a, Ar=C₆H₅, b, Ar=*p*.NO₂-C₆H₄, c, Ar=*o*.OH-C₆H₄,
d, Ar=*p*.OH-C₆H₄, e, Ar=*p*.OCH₃-C₆H₄,
f, Ar=*p*.N(OH)₂-C₆H₄

The presence of α,β-unsaturated ketonic group in compound 2, prompted us to interact it with hy-

drazines according to the method of Sammour and El-Kasaby⁹. Interaction of 2 with hydrazine hydrate in dry alcohol in presence of galcial acetic acid gave the corresponding 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-(*N*-acetylpyrazoline) (3a-f). However, the reaction of 2 with phenylhydrazine proceeded in dry alcohol in presence of piperidine afforded the corresponding 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-(*N*-phenylpyrazoline) (4a-f).

a, Ar=C₆H₅, b, Ar=*p*.NO₂-C₆H₄, c, Ar=*o*.OH-C₆H₄,
d, Ar=*p*.OH-C₆H₄, e, Ar=*p*.OCH₃-C₆H₄,
f, Ar=*p*.N(OH)₂-C₆H₄

Also, the activation exerted by the carbonyl group on the exocyclic double bond in these compounds render them available for the addition of various amino compounds, e.g. hydroxylamine hydrochloride, urea and thiourea^{10,11}. Interaction of 2 with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution gave the corresponding 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-oxazoline (5a-f), whereas the interaction of 2 with urea in ethanolic and hydrochloric acid media gave 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-pyrimidine derivatives (6a-f). On the other hand, interaction of 2 with thiourea in ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution lead to the formation of the corresponding pyrimidinethione derivatives (7a-f).

The structure of compounds 1-7 have been identified by elemental and ir spectral analyses. The

a, Ar=C₆H₅, b, Ar=p-NO₂-C₆H₄, c, Ar=o-OH-C₆H₄,
 d, Ar=p-OH-C₆H₄, e, Ar=p-OCH₃-C₆H₄,
 f, Ar=p-N(OH)₂-C₆H₄.

ir spectra^{1,2} of the compounds showed bands at 1 606-1 595 cm⁻¹ (C=C) for compounds 2a-f,

the absence of C=O band and the presence of band at 1 620-1 613 cm⁻¹ (C=N cyclic) for compounds 3a-f and 4a-f, whereas the spectra showed bands at 1 730-1 680 (C=O), 1 280 (C=S) and 1 493 cm⁻¹ (C-N-C=S) for the prepared compounds 6a-f and 7a-f, respectively.

The prepared Schiff bases and pyrimidinethione derivatives (1 and 7a) have also remarkable antibacterial activity against the same bacteria and fungi strains showing the high potency.

Experimental

The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Unicam SP 200 spectrophotometer. Melting points are uncorrected. Analytical and physical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazoline-5-(p-acetylaniline)
 (1): 1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolin-5-one and p-aminoacetophenone in equimolar ratio were dissolved in absolute ethanol and few drops of piperidine as catalyst added, and the mixture was refluxed for about 15 h. The reaction mixture was then evaporated under vacuum, and the resulting

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. *	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analyses N % ; Found/(Calcd.)
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolidene-p-acetylaniline					
2a	C ₆ H ₅	190	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O	11.40 (11.00)
2b	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	245	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂	13.50 (13.21)
2c	o-OH-C ₆ H ₄	160	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂	10.70 (10.68)
2d	p-OH-C ₆ H ₄	271	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂	10.80 (10.68)
2e	p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	115	90	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	10.40 (10.27)
2f	p-N(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	155	87	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O	18.60 (18.27)
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-(N-acetyl-N-phenyl)pyrazoline					
3a	C ₆ H ₅	110	97.8	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ N ₃ O	15.80 (16.09)
3b	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	140	89.3	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	17.40 (17.50)
3c	o-OH-C ₆ H ₄	130	75.9	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	15.10 (15.52)
3d	p-OH-C ₆ H ₄	150	9.1	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	15.00 (15.52)
3e	p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	180	18.18	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	14.80 (15.05)
3f	p-N(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	110	65.5	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ O	17.10 (17.57)
4a	C ₆ H ₅	200	27.27	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃	14.50 (14.99)
4b	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	130	95.24	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	16.20 (16.34)
4c	o-OH-C ₆ H ₄	210	13.6	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	14.10 (14.43)
4d	p-OH-C ₆ H ₄	120	9.1	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	14.00 (14.43)
4e	p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	165	16	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	14.00 (14.02)
4f	p-N(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	170-175	20	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃	16.20 (16.41)

(Table 1 contd.)

1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-oxazoline					
5a	C ₆ H ₅	195	16.7	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	18.90 (14.21)
5b	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	>300	12.5	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	15.70 (15.91)
5c	p-N(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	215	13.3	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	15.70 (16.02)
5d	p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	170	8	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	18.10 (18.21)
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-pyrimidine					
6a	C ₆ H ₅	200-205	83.3	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	16.30 (16.63)
6b	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	215	75	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	15.90 (15.48)
6c	p-N(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	195	58.3	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	17.80 (18.10)
6d	p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	205-210	33.3	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	15.40 (15.60)
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-pyrimidinethione					
7a	C ₆ H ₅	195	8.3	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ S	15.80 (16.02)
7b	p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	>300	16.7	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.30 (17.43)
7c	p-N(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	200	33.3	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ S	17.30 (17.50)
7d	p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	160	16.7	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS	14.70 (14.99)

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analyses.

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL SCREENING OF SOME COMPOUNDS

Organism	1	2a	2b	3a	3b	3f	4a	5a	5b	5e	6e	7a
Bacterial species												
<i>B. stearothermophilus</i> 92-L.N.	++++	++	-	-	+	+	++	+	-	+++	++	++
<i>B. stearothermophilus</i> 98-L.N.	+++	++	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	++	+	+++
<i>Sarcinalutea</i>	+++	+++	-	-	+	++	++	-	++	+	++	+++
<i>E. coli</i>	++	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	++	+++
Fungal species												
<i>Penicillium cyclospum</i>	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	overgrowth
<i>Aspergillus egyptiocus</i>	++	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+
<i>Alternaria</i>	+++	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-

(++++, +++)=High potency, (++)=Medium potency, (+)=Lower potency, (-)=No potency.

precipitate filtered off, washed with alcohol and recrystallised from alcohol giving **1**, m.p. 143-45° (Found: C, 74.10; H, 5.60; N, 14.80. Calcd.: C, 74.23; H, 5.84; N, 14.43%).

1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-chalcone (2a-f): To a solution of **1** (0.01 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol, two drops of piperidine were added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5-12 h, concentrated, cooled, filtered and the chalcones so obtained was purified as usual.

1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-(N-acetyl[N-phenyl]pyrazoline (3a-f/4a-f)): (i) To a solution of chalcones (**2a-f**; 1 g) in ethanol, hydrazine hydrate (50%, 8 ml) was added followed by

glacial acetic acid (10 ml), and the reaction mixture refluxed for 5-20 h. The solid that separated upon concentrating the reaction mixture was filtered and recrystallised from acetic acid. (ii) In the case of phenylhydrazine, the same ratio was used but piperidine was added as a catalyst.

1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-oxazoline (5a-f): A solution of chalcones (**2a-f**; 0.01 mol) was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of sodium hydroxide as catalyst for 5-20 h. The reaction mixture was then evaporated to dryness and triturated with petroleum ether (20 ml) when a resinous material deposited. The latter was triturated with water, and the separated product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-pyrimidine (6a-f): Equimolar ratio of ethanolic solution of **2** and urea in the presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid (2 ml) were refluxed for 12–20 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool, the precipitated products after neutralisation with 5 N NaOH was filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolideneazomethine-5-pyrimidinethione (7a-f): The above method was repeated but with thiourea.

Biological screening of the compounds using filter paper disc: Compounds **1**, **2a,b**, **3a,b,f**, **4a**, **5a,b,e**, **6e**, **7a** were dissolved in ethylene glycol. The bacteria and fungi used in these experiments were previously found to be susceptible to several soil microorganisms tested. Filter paper disc method was used for biological screening of bacteria and fungi; the results are reported in Table 2.

References

1. Z. H. KHALIL, and A. S. YANNI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 494.
2. P. B. GILLMAN, JR., R. T. BERRY, T. D. KOSZŁOK and S. ZIGMAN, U. S. Pat. 4 323 121/1980.
3. A. K. KALLAFALLA, M. Sc. Thesis, Assiut University, 1979.
4. A. K. KALLAFALLA, Ph.D. Thesis, Assiut University, 1982.
5. E. A. ABBAS, M.Sc. Thesis, Assiut University, 1985.
6. S. YAMZOR, Japan Pat. 75 158 542/1975.
7. M. V. POUSTYANOV and E. V. LOGNACHEN, *Kov. Tekst. Khim.*, 1974, **3**, 74.
8. Monsanto Co., Japan Pat. 76 35 430/1976.
9. A. SAMMOUR and M. EL-KASABY, *UARJ. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 243.
10. A. SAMMOUR, A. ABD-ELRAOUF, M. EL-KASABY and M. A. HASSAN, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1972, **15**, 429.
11. A. K. KALLAFALLA, M.Sc. Thesis, Assiut University, 1979.
12. L. J. BELLANY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", 2nd. ed., Methuen, London, 1958.